

A Study on Numerical Simulation of Rayleigh Benard Convection Flow Pattern

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Abstract:

The flow pattern created in the Rayleigh-Bénard convection has been numerically simulated to gain a deeper knowledge of flow mechanics and Rayleigh-Bénard convection phenomenon. A rectangular channel of 288.5 mm length and height of 119.4 mm [1] was used with water as the working fluid. The Boussinesq approximation was used to simulate the physical effects of Rayleigh-Bénard convection.

Keywords: Rayleigh-Bénard Convection, Boussinesq approximation

1. Introduction:

One of the most basic and extensively researched types of natural convection is Rayleigh-Bénard convection, where heat transfer in a fluid occurs due to the movement of the fluid itself. This phenomenon happens in the fluid system when it is heated in the bottom section and cooled from above, leading to the formation of convection cells due to buoyancy forces that drive the fluid motion. It is named after the British scientist Lord Rayleigh, who first mathematically analyzed the instability that causes convection in 1916, and Henri Bénard, who experimentally observed the pattern formation in 1900. It has been researched for a long time and is becoming more and more popular because of its close relationship to numerous engineering applications, including heat exchangers and solar collectors.

The Rayleigh number (Ra), a dimensionless quantity that represents the equilibrium between buoyant and viscous forces in a fluid, determines the beginning of convection. Convection starts when the Rayleigh number rises above a particular threshold. This number depends on the fluid's thermal properties, thickness and temperature differential. From the movement of tectonic plates in the Earth's mantle to the design of effective heat exchangers, studying Rayleigh-Bénard convection aids in our understanding of the dynamics of heat transfer in a variety of natural and industrial scenarios.

Despite its apparent simplicity, the Rayleigh-Bénard setup involves a complex phenomenon with a wide range of behaviours. Conduction is the primary method of heat transport at low Rayleigh numbers, which maintains system stability. Convection begins as the Rayleigh number increases, resulting in various convection patterns, such as square or hexagonal cells, which are controlled by the dimensions of the geometry and aspect ratio of the fluid layer. The flow may become turbulent when the Rayleigh number rises to extremely high values, which would further complicate the behaviour of the convection cells.

Understanding the basic ideas of fluid dynamics and heat transport, as well as its applications in practical engineering systems and natural phenomena, requires an understanding of Rayleigh-Bénard convection. For example, it provides insight into the evolution of ocean currents, large-scale atmospheric patterns. Its importance in both industrial applications and scientific study emphasizes how crucial it is to investigate this field

The conceptual foundations of Rayleigh-Bénard convection with the conditions that cause convection, and the effects of fluid characteristics and system geometry on convection cell behaviour are all explored in this study. Deeper understanding of the intricate dynamics of this event will be possible through the use of numerical simulations.

R-B convection branching sequences for 3-D enclosures with rectangular geometry and insulated sidewalls and small aspect ratios were investigated numerically by Mukutmoni and Yang [2]. Walls at the bottom and top are heated and cooled isothermally and except for the fluid's temperature-dependent viscosity, the Boussinesq approximation is used. Accordingly, the aspect ratios of 2.42 and 1.23 have been used. The value of Prandtl number is taken as 5. With the increase in Rayleigh number, the calculations precisely mirrored the bifurcation sequence shown in the tests.

Four different aspect ratio areas are categorized based on the several flow patterns in Hébert et al.'s [3] experimental study of R-B convection in cylindrical containers with varying aspect ratios. The fluid is assumed to be a normal fluid with density as a linearly varying function of the temperature in the majority of the studies previously cited. Nonetheless, there are several unique fluids found in nature and engineering whose densities reach extreme values at particular temperatures. At a temperature of about 4 °C, the density of water, which is a standard fluid, reaches its maximum value. [4–6].

To enhance comprehension of the characteristics of Rayleigh-Benard convection, Yu-Peng Hu et al. [7] used DNS in a rectangular enclosure with water at nearly its maximum density and aspect ratio of 2. DNS was carried out with finite volume method. Effect of maximum density was evident on Rayleigh-Bénard convection phenomena. Under the same control parameters, the rectangular cavity's overall capacity for heat transfer is improved.

2. Numerical Simulation:

The current numerical simulation was run using FLUENT 14.0, a commercially available CFD program. The continuity, momentum, and energy conservation equations were used to solve the convection heat transfer model, as shown below:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (\rho \cdot V) = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\rho V)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \cdot V \cdot V) = -\nabla \cdot P + \nabla \cdot [\mu \cdot (\nabla \cdot V + \nabla \cdot V')] + F = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\rho \cdot E)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot [V \cdot (\rho \cdot E + P)] = \nabla \cdot (k_{eff} \nabla T) + S_h = 0 \quad (3)$$

To formulate the steady state condition, solver based on pressure is used.

Solver : Pressure Based

Time study : Steady state

Models : Viscous – Laminar

: Energy

Figure 1: Boundary Conditions of the Rectangular enclosure along with the geometry

A mapped meshing is generated in the geometry created with a uniform spacing within the domain. A grid independence study is carried out by varying mesh element size keeping other parameters constant. In order to carryout grid independence study, the simulation results of surface heat transfer coefficient for different mesh sizes are taken as given in Table 1.

Table 1: Grid Independence Study

Mesh Element size	Computational Elements	Heat Transfer Coefficient
0.004	2190	8.21
0.0002	8700	8.20
0.0001	34680	8.19
0.00005	137903	8.18

Every mesh element size displays quite similar results, as can be seen in the table. The grid size of 0.0001 was selected after taking into account both the computing time and the numerical accuracy.

3. Results and Discussion:

Multiple flow patterns that have been seen in numerous earlier tests results associated with Rayleigh Benard convection. The current study uses numerical simulations to observe the Rayleigh Benard convection flow pattern at a system pressure of 1 bar and Rayleigh number of 108.66. Simulations of for water in a rectangular channel has been performed. Flow pattern identified in the channel can be validated with numerous past experiments.

In the present simulation, a two-circle pattern flow along the height of the geometry has been observed in the domain which can be clearly seen in the figure 5. It is evident from figure 2 to figure 5 that convection was developed due to the buoyancy effect generated because of the temperature potential created by bottom and top wall of the rectangular geometry. A temperature gradient can be seen in the +ve Y direction as the R-B convection occurs from bottom to the to the top side of the wall which can be observed in figure 6 of the temperature profile.

Figure 2: Velocity Contour

Figure 3: Velocity Contour in X-Direction

Figure 4: Velocity Contour in Y-Direction

Figure 5: Contour of Stream Function

Figure 6: Temperature profile

4. Conclusions:

The current numerical simulation presents the generation of flow pattern for Rayleigh-Bénard convection with maximum density water in rectangular enclosure. The current numerical simulation was run using FLUENT 14.0, a commercially available CFD program. a two-circle pattern flow along the height of the geometry has been observed in the domain which can be clearly indicates the presence of Rayleigh-Bénard convection effects in the closed enclosure. Convection currents were developed to the buoyancy effect created as a result of the temperature difference created between the horizontal surfaces of the rectangular enclosure.

NOMENCLATURE

E	Energy per unit mass (J/kg)
ρ	Density (kg/m ³)
S _h	Energy source term (kg/m-s ³)
σ	Surface tension (N/m)
Eff	Effective
V	Volume
P	Pressure (Pa)
μ	Dynamic viscosity (N-s/m ²)
T	Temperature (K)

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